

CRITERION INDICATORS REPRESENTING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF AGRICULTURE

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Abstract: The economic reforms carried out in the agrarian sector require the introduction of market relations in the innovative development system. As noted, the transfer of the innovative development of the agrarian sector to market principles is associated with a number of problems. In particular, the issue of establishing contractual relations between consumers of innovative products regarding purchase and its introduction is considered one of the main tasks.

Keywords: innovative product, innovative supply of agriculture, soil fertility.

It is known that the issue of creation of innovative developments in innovative-research institutions belonging to the agricultural sector and its transformation into a commodity product and its sale to consumers has become one of the complex problems since a long time ago. The issue of determining the price of an innovative product in the contract concluded between innovative research institutes and consumers of innovative products is quite complicated. Because, on the one hand, the price of an innovative product should cover the costs incurred for research (experimentation, implementation) and provide a certain level of profit to the researcher. On the other hand, the consumer of the product (the buyer or the sponsor of the research work) tries to ensure that the benefit from the introduction of the innovative product is higher than the benefit from the existing technology and to be able to cover the costs in the short term.

Generally, based on market laws, R&D institutions, as sellers, try to increase the price of the innovative product, while buyers of the innovative product try to lower the price of the product. That is why it is difficult to set a price for an innovative product, and no single method has been developed in this regard. However, both in the previous system and now, this problem is of interest to both scientists and specialists and is conducting research in various directions.

The calculation of the cost of scientific and research works was carried out on the basis of the expenses of departments, laboratories and sectors operating

in the institutes. In this case, a mechanism for stimulating the reduction of the cost of research work was not developed, while maintaining the staff table (number of researchers) that was in practice until this period.

The most important thing is that when setting contract prices for innovative products, the efficiency of production due to the use of innovative products was not taken into account, as well as the quality of innovative products was not expressed.

Due to the lack of real market relations in the innovative supply of agriculture, the pricing of the topics determined by the state for research is determined not based on the relevance and complexity of the topic, but based on the amount of funds allocated from the budget. This does not take into account the supply and demand for innovative products.

Setting a price for the results of scientific research gives an opportunity to introduce market relations in the field. The lack of a scientifically based price made it impossible to carry out the work of transferring the innovative supply of the industry to the economic account.

Pricing of the innovative product, in turn, requires the development of a pricing mechanism for the innovative product according to the directions of the industry, and the development of different models of the pricing mechanism. The first condition for setting a price for an innovative product is to ensure that the price takes into account the interests of both parties, as noted above. Such price flexibility should be taken into account, especially when determining research and development costs, and the aspects that facilitate the adoption and adoption of an innovative product.

Research and development results in specific characteristics of agriculture, including creation of new varieties of plants, increase of soil fertility, increase of productivity of livestock, protection of plants and so on. It should be taken into account that these and other research works in the agricultural field are related to living organisms. The vagaries of nature also affect the results of research and development in agriculture. Unlike industrial production in agriculture, it is very difficult to predict the results of scientific research.

Scientific research results of agricultural scientists are associated with a number of risks. In particular, the creation of a new variety of cotton is associated with the crossbreeding of the first tens of thousands of plants. Of the 100% new lines created by breeders, only 28-30% are put into the institute's selection. In this test, only 20-23% of the lines are submitted to the State Variety Selection System for evaluation. 3-4% of this can be recommended for planting

on a large scale in farms. We gave this example in order to draw attention to the difficulties and processes associated with pricing the final product of research and development.

All of these measures should be taken into account when setting a price for an innovative product. In addition, the pricing model created for one type of product may not be appropriate for another type of product. Because each type of innovative product created has its own characteristics. The use of innovative products (plant varieties, production technology and hokoza) is carried out through the cultivation of agricultural products. In this way, the costs are transferred to the manufactured products, to the price of cotton, grain, meat, water and other types of products. This process takes place within 20 years for selective varieties of plants, 25 years for orchards and vineyards, and for their standard service life for newly created technologies.

Based on the market relations between the consumers of the innovative product and the institutions, when setting the price for the innovative product, the specific features mentioned above should also be taken into account. Of course, it will not be correct to monopolize the price of an innovative product by research institutes. Therefore, the interests of both sides should be taken into account when setting the price. In the introduction of an innovative innovation (a new variety, technology, technique, etc.), several interacting enterprises are involved. These are scientific-research institutions, experimental farms, seed farms producing elite and various reproductive seeds, seed cleaning plants, design bureaus, machinery manufacturing plants, etc. The economic efficiency of the innovative innovation being put into practice will be created with the participation of these enterprises. Therefore, this characteristic should be taken into account in market conditions. All this shows how difficult it is to set a price for an innovative product. That is probably why the method of pricing innovative products in agriculture has not yet been developed. Innovative product pricing methods created at the end of the 80s of the last century are used in the institutes conducting innovative research in the industrial sector¹.

The price of an innovative product is determined based on the combination of research results and net profit: a certain amount of net profit is added to the estimate of research and development costs, based on the cost of the product or wages. In other words, the pricing of an innovative product is determined based on the cost mechanism through the following system:

$$H = T * Fm \quad (1)$$

¹ Source; The Law of Selection. Newspaper "Narodnoe slovo", September 11, 1996

Here, H - is the price of an innovative product; T is the cost of the innovative product; F_m - is a certain amount of profit rate.

However, this method does not allow to determine the price of an innovative product. When setting a price for an innovative product in agriculture, it is necessary to take into account the value of the product obtained at the expense of the introduction of scientific research results, the share of scientific research institutes and the volume of introduction of innovative newness.

It is known that the price of an innovative product is the amount of expenses incurred by the entity creating the product, and the amount of profit, on the other hand, includes the price offered by the consumer, the amount of profit expected from the introduction of the innovative product based on his purchasing power.

Based on the above, it is appropriate to base the economic efficiency obtained from one hectare of cultivated area at the expense of a new scientific solution. In this case, the following issues should be taken as a basis:

- rate of increase in productivity of agricultural crops due to the introduction of new innovative development (X_o);
- level of increase in the quality of agricultural products grown due to the introduction of new innovative development (S_i);
- level of labor cost reduction (IK) within one hectare of cultivated area due to the introduction of new innovative development;
- the level of reduction of material and technical costs (MT) within one hectare of cultivated area due to the introduction of new innovative development;

The final result obtained here must be greater than or equal to "1", otherwise it is considered that the economic benefit from the introduction of a new innovative result has not been achieved and a decision is made to reject it.

As we mentioned above, in the conditions of market relations, the use of innovative results in production should be carried out based on the sales contract concluded between the parties. The duties and rights of the parties to this contract should be fully expressed. This should be an important condition of the contract, because an innovative product, unlike other branded products, can be resold several times. Therefore, the conclusion of the contract on the finished innovative product provides an opportunity for the scientific research institute or the author to retain the right to resell the product. If the innovative product is financed by the customer in the process of scientific research, in this case, the

customer must give a certain part of the money received by the institute (or the author) from the sale of the innovative product to another consumer. This should be indicated in the contract by agreement of both parties.

These two issues are the repeated sale of an innovative product and giving a part of the profit (or selling price) received by the institution from another consumer to the wholesaler. Therefore, an innovative product is distinguished by its unique characteristics compared to other products.

Pricing for contract sales of innovative products (varieties) in cotton and grain production may be somewhat lighter than in other areas. Because it is clear how many areas each farm will plant. But upfront pricing for all types of innovative products is fraught with challenges. Especially when introducing technology, new techniques.

It should also be taken into account that a new variety or new technology and technique, in general, an innovative product by itself does not produce the effect indicated by the author. For this, it is necessary to create conditions for this innovative product to produce the specified result. It is up to the consumers of the innovative product to create these conditions, and the specified result can be obtained only when they fully follow the given recommendations. However, much depends on the discipline of those involved in the implementation process. In addition, various anomalous conditions (rainfall, drought, various natural disasters, etc.) also affect the effectiveness of innovative products from economic conditions. Of course, it is difficult to take into account all these innovative product pricing. This situation also does not give the opportunity to fully implement the proposal to transfer a part of the results obtained from the introduction of the above-mentioned scientific result to the economic scientific-research institute.

A number of practical studies, including the creation of new varieties of agricultural crops, the development of their cultivation technology, the creation of certain types of new machines, the creation of chemicals, the development of recommendations for the organization of production, the use of machinery, aimed at ensuring the economy of water resources and other scientific - only the results of practical research can be sold as goods.

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